

INFRAEDI-02-2018

www.bioexcel.eu

BioExcel-2 Project Number 823830

D1.3 – Updated software roadmaps

WP1: Code Optimization & Scaling

Copyright© 2019-2021 The partners of the BioExcel Consortium

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Document Information

Deliverable Number	D1.3
Deliverable Name	Updated software roadmaps
Due Date	2019-11-30 (PM11)
Deliverable Lead	KTH
Authors	Berk Hess (KTH) Paul Bauer (KTH) Erik Lindahl (KTH) Rodrigo Honorato (UU) Alexandre Bonvin (UU) Brian Jimenez-Garcia (UU) Arno Proeme (UEDIN) Dmitry Morozov (JYU) Gerrit Groenhof (JYU) Bert L. de Groot (MPG) Vytautas Gapsys (MPG)
Keywords	Software development, roadmap, exascale computing, modularization, workflows
WP	WP1
Nature	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Final Version Date	2019-11-27
Reviewed by	Rosa Badia (IRB) Stian Soiland-Reyes (UNIMAN)
MGT Board Approval	2019-11-27
MGT Board Approval of revision	2020-12-15

Document History

Partner	Date	Comments	Version
KTH	2019-10-01	First draft, gromacs text	0.1
KTH	2019-10-12	Added intro	0.2
KTH	2019-10-28	Integrated text from all codes	0.3
UEDIN	2019-10-28	Updated CP2K text	0.4
KTH	2019-11-07	Response to EB review	0.5
KTH	2019-11-13	Response to more EB review	0.6
KTH	2019-11-13	Merged comments from JYU	0.7
BSC	2019-11-14	Updates from EB review	0.8
UNIMAN	2019-11-25	Updates from EB review	0.9
KTH	2019-11-26	Minor edits in response to review	0.10
MPG	2019-11-26	Updates	0.11
KTH	2019-11-27	Finale edits	0.12
KTH	2020-12-08	Add appendix with code status	0.13

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the present state of the BioExcel-2 core application roadmaps, how user and infrastructure needs have been prioritized, the specific tasks this corresponds to in the codes, and what the long-term directions of the codes are – even beyond the present BioExcel funding period. As part of BioExcel-2, the software roadmaps have been updated to balance development driven by user requests for features as well as strategic efforts targeting EuroHPC and preparing for next-generation processor and accelerator hardware.

The **GROMACS** development will focus on a number of key user-requested features, in particular adding multiple time stepping, driving simulations with external data, facilitating generation of input data, and better free energy tools. The development of performance optimization for additional new platforms will also continue together with efforts targeting significantly improved scaling by using ensemble parallelism, as well as co-design projects to port the code to new accelerator platforms.

The development of the **PMX** package will follow two main directions. Firstly, the core code will be updated with the changes necessary for the successful future usability of the software. In particular, with the end of Python2 lifetime, pmx will be fully rewritten in Python3. The continuous support of the main pmx functionalities will be ensured. The second major development direction comprises the incorporation of features frequently requested by users, the addition of new mutation libraries and creation of workflows for free energy calculation setup and analysis.

HADDOCK's development focuses on the continuous improvement of the web server, which functions as the main user's interface, the implementation of relevant features and the design of a new modular version, HADDOCK3. The web server is being co-developed alongside the local HADDOCK version, so that new features (coarse-grained and shape docking, etc.) are readily available in an intuitive and responsive user-friendly interface. A major rework of the current code is in place, for what will become HADDOCK3, with this modular design we aim to provide flexibility for workflow creation and a straightforward framework to integrate new tools. This new modular architecture will also enable more efficient execution on HPC resources.

To provide users with access to chemical reactivity in biomolecular simulations, we will develop an interface between GROMACS and CP2K, a highly parallelized density functional theory (DFT) computer program. With the new interface, users can perform multi-scale simulations, in which one part of the system is modelled with DFT, while the remainder is described with a molecular mechanics force field (i.e. QM/MM). Our developments focus on providing the community with an accurate, scalable and user-friendly QM/MM solution. Compared to the previous BioExcel software roadmap, which focused on CPMD for DFT functionality in QM/MM simulations, this updated roadmap reflects the project's transition to CP2K, which has more wide-spread availability and uptake in the community.

Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	7
2	GENERAL REQUIREMENTS OF ADVANCED BIOMOLECULAR SOFTWARE	8
3	LONG TERM DEVELOPMENT PLANS FOR GROMACS	9
3.1	EVOLUTION OF EXASCALE-SUITABLE TASK PARALLELISM	10
3.2	DEPLOYMENT AND ACCELERATION FOR NEW EUROHPC ARCHITECTURES.....	10
3.3	ENABLE ACCELERATOR/GPU-ONLY SIMULATIONS	11
3.4	AUTOMATED PERFORMANCE OPTIMIZATION	11
3.5	SIMPLE DOUBLING OF PERFORMANCE THROUGH MULTIPLE TIME STEPPING	11
3.6	SUPPORT FOR FAST MULTIPOLE ELECTROSTATICS FOR BETTER SCALING	12
3.7	SUPPORT FOR TABULATED INTERACTIONS FOR CPU AND GPU ARCHITECTURES.....	12
3.8	SUPPORT FOR POLARIZABLE FORCE FIELDS.....	12
3.9	IMPROVE FREE-ENERGY PERFORMANCE	13
3.10	SIMPLIFIED FREE-ENERGY CALCULATIONS.....	13
3.11	IMPLEMENT LONG-TERM STABLE C++ AND PYTHON LIBRARY APIS.....	13
3.12	STREAMLINING OF SIMULATION PREPARATION TOOLS	13
3.13	EXPANSION AND MODERNIZATION OF TRAJECTORY-ANALYSIS TOOL SUITE	14
3.14	CONSTANT-PH SIMULATIONS.....	14
3.15	MOLECULAR DYNAMICS FOR LARGE SYSTEMS	14
3.16	FLEXIBLE INPUT FORMAT.....	15
3.17	DRIVING SIMULATIONS FROM EXTERNAL INPUTS.....	15
3.18	SUPPORT FOR MARKOV STATE MODEL ENSEMBLE PARALLELISM.....	15
3.19	SUPPORT FOR HADDOCK FUNCTIONALITY.....	15
4	LONG TERM DEVELOPMENT PLANS FOR HADDOCK	16
4.1	HADDOCK2.4 WEB SERVER.....	16
4.1.1	<i>Expanding the server with pre-defined docking scenarios</i>	18
4.1.2	<i>Result visualization</i>	19
4.1.3	<i>Results export</i>	20
4.2	HADDOCK2.4.....	20
4.3	HADDOCK3.....	20
4.3.1	<i>Modular workflows</i>	21
4.3.2	<i>Exascale interactome modelling</i>	22
4.4	VIRTUALIZATION	22
5	LONG TERM DEVELOPMENT PLANS FOR QM/MM WITH CP2K AND GROMACS	23
5.1	CREATION OF ROBUST, SCALABLE GROMACS-CP2K INTERFACE FOR QM/MM	23
5.1.1	<i>Prototyping using existing implementation of QM/MM interface in GROMACS</i>	23
5.1.2	<i>Modularization of the interface within GROMACS MdModules framework</i>	24
5.1.3	<i>Extending parallelization of the CP2K interface for efficient usage of existing GROMACS capabilities</i>	24
5.2	OPTIMIZATION OF CP2K FOR QM/MM THROUGH GROMACS-CP2K INTERFACE	25
5.2.1	<i>Optimization of GEEP subroutines</i>	25
5.2.2	<i>Improvement of Quickstep DFT load balancing for biomolecular QM/MM</i>	25
5.2.3	<i>Optimization of CP2K subroutines and DBCSR GPU acceleration identified by performance analysis of the GROMACS-CP2K interface</i>	26
5.3	IMPLEMENTATION OF EFFICIENT OPTIMIZERS AND TRANSITION PATH METHODS IN GROMACS	26
5.3.1	<i>Update L-BFGS optimizer in GROMACS</i>	26
5.3.2	<i>Micro-iterations for multiscale systems optimization</i>	27
5.3.3	<i>Implementation of Nudged Elastic Band method (NEB) for optimizations of transition states in GROMACS</i>	27
6	LONG TERM DEVELOPMENT PLANS FOR PMX	28
6.1	PLANS FOR THE CORE CODE AND USABILITY	28
6.1.1	<i>Python3</i>	28
6.1.2	<i>Conda</i>	28

6.1.3	<i>Further modularization</i>	28
6.2	MUTATION LIBRARIES	29
6.2.1	<i>New libraries</i>	29
6.2.2	<i>Automated tests for mutation libraries</i>	29
6.2.3	<i>Unified amino acid and DNA mutation libraries</i>	29
6.3	FEATURES	29
6.3.1	<i>Amino acid protonation</i>	29
6.3.2	<i>Post-translational modifications</i>	30
6.3.3	<i>Covalent modifications</i>	30
6.3.4	<i>Workflows</i>	30
7	ROADMAPS	31
	APPENDIX: STATUS OF PILOT CODES	35
	GROMACS CODE DEVELOPMENT STATUS	35
	GROMACS MODULAR CODE DEVELOPMENT STATUS	36
	HADDOCK CODE DEVELOPMENT STATUS.....	37
	HADDOCK WEB SERVER DEVELOPMENT STATUS	39
	HADDOCK3.0 MODULAR CODE DEVELOPMENT STATUS	41
	PMX STATUS	42
	CP2K STATUS	44

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents updates of roadmaps presented in BioExcel deliverable “D1.3 Roadmap of future hardware and long-term development plan for each pilot application” in April 2017 (<https://zenodo.org/record/574605>). Comparing with that deliverable, the code quantum mechanics code CP2K has been added and CPMD has is no longer present.

One of the most important impact items for BioExcel-2 is that the Centre-of-Excellence supports, maintains, and develops some of the most widely used software in the field of computational biomolecular science. These codes are used by thousands of academic and industrial research groups, they have enabled dozens of projects in PRACE and other international HPC organizations, and many of the codes are highly involved in co-design efforts with industry to design next-generation hardware as well as software that is better at addressing concrete scientific and industrial challenges.

BioExcel-2 (as BioExcel) is a highly user-driven CoE: Investments in software and support are prioritized based on the impact the work will have for users. This has been based on questionnaires, user feedback at BioExcel workshops and forums, as well as in-depth interviews with selected users and industry site visits. Many of the features currently on the code roadmaps have originated this way, but there are also critically important challenges to the entire field that might not be immediately obvious to individual users, such as e.g.:

- making sure codes will run efficiently on future (ideally European) hardware yet to be announced,
- implementing acceleration for multi-GPU systems likely to be common in the pre-Exascale EuroHPC installations,
- developing solutions to make it possible for communities previously not using large-scale HPC to move to this type of resources, e.g. through better handling of massive I/O, throughput-focused computing, and big data,
- achieving scaling on systems with order-of-magnitude more processors than what is available today to target the Exascale systems, for instance by moving to ensemble techniques for small systems,
- achieving interoperability between all major codes in the field to enable completely new types of workflows, while also prioritizing mutual interoperability between leading European HPC codes,
- leading rather than merely participating in the international community, e.g. by ensuring *all* common codes produce similar results, and helping users (as well as the community) to make better choices,
- sharing knowledge such that advances by BioExcel can also be implemented in other codes,

Challenges like these have been prioritized based on input e.g. from the PRACE SSC Scientific Case, the user needs, benchmarks and hosting reports from EuroHPC, roadmaps from the European Processor Initiative, and several international organizations. BioExcel and BioExcel-2 have also been established strategic collaboration with the US-based MolSSI center, we have organized and participated in a number of joint workshops to promote code interoperability, and

in addition the BioExcel Scientific Director sits on several scientific advisory boards of centers maintaining other key codes such as NAMD and VMD, which has led to a number of close collaborations and aligned strategic plans that have the potential to fundamentally transform how researchers use all the codes in the field, not only the ones maintained within BioExcel.

As there has been preceding work in the context of the first BioExcel project on three of the four pilot codes including in BioExcel-2, we describe code features and health in tables that can be found in an appendix at the end of this document. This is to clarify what work has been done in the different projects. There are details for GROMACS, HADDOCK and pmx. As CP2K was not part of the first BioExcel project and there was no GROMACS-CP2K QMMM coupling at the start of BioExcel-2, no table has been included for CP2K. The tables also includes planned features which were known to be planned at the writing of this document.

2 General requirements of advanced biomolecular software

Scientific computing in general, and life science in particular, has large requirements not only for scaling, performance and features, but even more for quality assurance, extensive testing, ability to compare algorithms and results, having access to the code to critically assess an implementation, and strong provenance of results such as tracking exact source code versions and compilers used to be able to identify bugs or deviations.

In addition, users increasingly need to combine a number of different tools in workflows (adding demands for data interoperability), while using very flexible ways of generating input data through interactive options such as graphical interfaces or websites.

Encouraged by users, developer communities are working towards common terminologies and specifications across codes, to improve portability of results and settings.

Growing in importance for a variety of users is support for new hardware with emerging accelerator platforms, in particular to handle data growing in throughput, size and frequency of processing. An ongoing challenge, particular for industry users, is the desire to combine dedicated private compute infrastructure with on-demand scaling to cloud resources, which implies supporting a more heterogeneous and diverse set of hardware, operating systems and data management strategies.

Of increasing importance is flexible *installation options*. A system administrator might prefer standard Linux packages, while other sites need to customize installations. As an example, users in industry or strongly controlled environments have expressed needs for downloading a plain binary that can be run from a home directory without having to request an administrator to add or update a package across their company-wide IT infrastructure.

While BioExcel itself cannot solve all of these needs, they have been critical components in the development and prioritization of all software roadmaps in the CoE.

3 Long term development plans for GROMACS

For GROMACS a large number of important directions for future development have been identified. These are listed here but are not ordered into a formal timeline.

In practice, requirements from other funding resources will shift over time, and rarely can any developer focus solely on one task in order to deliver it by a predictable date, given that a feature often depends on several other features and that the development team also spends an increasing part of their time on quality assurance (QA) of previously completed features.

The skill set of available developers often determines which targets can receive most effort. Progress is also contingent upon the availability of resources for testing, and since GROMACS has moved to a full formal code review process, this also requires time and availability for the review of the code by other expert developers.

It should be noted that GROMACS does not only target bio-molecular simulations, and the software is increasingly being used in other areas. For the first time, several of the planned targets reflect the needs of other domains like materials science simulations.

Finally, as part of BioExcel and the mission of supporting all types of simulations for the community, the GROMACS project has started much closer collaborations (in particular for training) with Amber & NAMD, which are the other two major codes in the field, and these new collaborations are likely to influence future development of all codes.

Several items indicated on the previous roadmap have been partially or fully resolved by now, with features such as enhanced sampling techniques (the accelerated weight histogram method (AWH)) available in GROMACS 2018, as well as support for PME on GPU, the initial support for the Python API in GROMACS 2019 together with extended OpenCL accelerator support to improve performance on AMD and Intel GPUs, and now complete simulations running on NVIDIA GPUs and the ability to use experimental data to drive simulations in the upcoming GROMACS 2020 release.

Over the past years we have made major advances in performance, features and code organization and quality. There have also been improvements in usability, especially for new functionality, but this will be a stronger focus in the current plans.

For performance, more parts of the computation have been ported to be able to execute on GPUs. GROMACS has also been ported to the newest SIMD architectures. The inclusion of the *accelerated weight histogram* method enables accelerated sampling with a simple user interface and this method has already proven to be popular with users.

Many error messages have been clarified and more checks on user input have been added. The GROMACS test coverage has been expanded to improve reliability. To enable all this, a significant amount of refactoring and rewriting of legacy code has taken place. Although this has taken quite some time, it pays off in maintainability and provides better extensibility over the next years.

During 2019 the Python API has been integrated. This a major advance for usability and flexibility, as it enables interaction with GROMACS at the Python scripting level. All GROMACS tools are exposed in the API. Users can now work interactively with GROMACS in Python, or write high-level scripts that can be reused.

We have incorporated restraining functionality for experimental density data, such as from e.g. cryo-electron microscopy, to enable high quality refinement. Last but not least, there have been several performance improvements in existing algorithms, in particular for free-energy calculations.

3.1 Evolution of Exascale-suitable task parallelism

In particular when combined with domain decomposition between nodes, the rapidly increasing core counts is making it difficult to parallelize all tasks over all cores due to the limited size of data on each node. To address this, GROMACS will work on reformulating the entire molecular dynamics simulation algorithm into fine-grained task graphs where each task only runs on a subset of cores, communication is also formulated as tasks, and dynamic data dependency tracking to avoid global barriers. Presently there are few if any task libraries that support the type of extremely low-latency tasks needed. Therefore we are both evaluating the new OpenMP 5.0 task features while also working with two vendors on co-design projects that involve future task libraries.

3.2 Deployment and acceleration for new EuroHPC architectures

We are continuously improving the GROMACS SIMD acceleration layer to target all major platforms and have recently started a new co-design project focused on the ARM Scalable Vector Extensions (SVE). The code also takes advantage of GPU accelerators and now supports the calculation of close to all interaction types on those devices for CUDA-based platforms, and non-bonded short-range interactions and PME long-range interactions on devices that support OpenCL.

For 2020, GROMACS will focus on extended OpenCL support to both AMD and Intel platforms, improved multi-GPU scaling for CUDA, and beyond this we have new co-design projects targeting native acceleration for both CUDA, SYCL and HIP that

covers all current major accelerator vendors (NVIDIA, AMD, Intel). We are monitoring EuroHPC developments, if they select a different API for a potential European accelerator, we would also be highly interested in implementing support for this hardware assuming development resources are available.

3.3 Enable Accelerator/GPU-only simulations

We are working on adding support for GPU-only execution of MD simulations. This will remove the bottleneck where high-end GPUs presently must be paired with an expensive CPU, and it should significantly simplify the execution setup for users. Initially this port will only support CUDA as well as plain simulations using default thermostats/barostats, and in a second stage we are planning to add more functionality.

We would like to extend this to all major accelerator platforms, but that will likely require additional development resources. Longer-term, this should also enable a setup where the code can run e.g. 10-100 steps on the accelerator, and then returning to an outer loop running on a CPU to calculate complex algorithms such as density-driven fitting or other methods whose forces can be applied with multiple time stepping - this should combine CPU-independent performance with full flexibility.

3.4 Automated performance optimization

With ever more components of GROMACS being supported for GPU offload, it becomes ever more challenging for users to reach optimal performance for a given simulation system on given hardware. There are simply too many combinations of options to try, and while BioExcel have developed short-run benchmarks, they may not always give a realistic picture as performance characteristics depend also on individual simulation data and settings.

This challenge should be addressed by a combination of pre-computed cross-over points and auto-tuning during simulation by dynamically moving computation between CPU and GPU depending on load and actual performance. This will help unlock the full GROMACS performance for every user.

3.5 Simple doubling of performance through multiple time stepping

Currently GROMACS supports doubling of the time-step, and a near doubling of the performance, by replacing hydrogen atoms by *virtual interactions sites*. The disadvantages of this approach are that the topology is (automatically) modified, extra particles appear in the output and it is not supported for general small (drug) molecules. The same performance can be achieved through a multiple time stepping algorithm where most of the force calculation is only performed every second step. This approach is nearly transparent for the user. It only requires setting one option for the integrator and no topology modifications.

3.6 Support for fast multipole electrostatics for better scaling

GROMACS, like most molecular simulation packages, use the *particle-mesh Ewald* (PME) to compute long-range electrostatics interactions. PME achieves high serial performance through the use of *fast Fourier transforms* (FFTs), but these strongly limit parallel scaling due to the higher number of communications required.

A hierarchical method such as the *fast-multipole method* (FMM) has much lower communication needs and therefore provides better scaling, which becomes critical when scaling large systems to millions of cores. A fundamental issue with FMM has been that it does not conserve energy, which is a requirement for molecular dynamics. Recently we have developed and demonstrated improvements to FMM to obtain energy conservation. This paves the way for the application of FMM to molecular dynamics. We are working with two leading groups in Europe and Japan to incorporate their FMM codes in GROMACS.

3.7 Support for tabulated interactions for CPU and GPU architectures

Many knowledge-based force fields, particularly in materials science, produce interaction functions that are not based on an easily described mathematical formula. The potential and force for such interactions must be looked up from tables for each particle pair. The use of such kernels needs care because one must choose interpolation schemes that are able to run fast on the hardware, while providing a bounded error.

To make use of such tabulated interactions, the topology description within GROMACS must be extended so that it is possible to choose tables for unique atom pairs, or pairs of all types, etc. This would significantly enhance the usability of GROMACS for non-traditional applications, including both materials science and special potentials currently only available on slow or non-scaling simulation codes.

3.8 Support for polarizable force fields

Most biomolecular simulations and calculations are performed with force fields with fixed partial charges. Although this works quite well, this is an approximation as it ignores atomic polarizability. Atomic polarizability can have a large effect on interactions when molecules or groups of atoms change the environment, like during the binding of a drug molecule.

GROMACS has long supported the so-called *shell model* for atomic polarizability. But with the expanding efforts on polarizable force fields over the last decade supporting other polarization models is possible. Collaborators are working on an implementation of the polarizable version of the popular CHARMM force field in GROMACS, this work should be integrated. Furthermore, it can be useful, in particular for polarizable models, to describe charges as a distribution instead of point charges. Support for this needs to be added in the pair-interaction kernels.

3.9 Improve free-energy performance

Free-energy calculations are an important class of calculation in GROMACS, both for academia and (pharmaceutical) industry. They are used, for example, during drug development. These are typical throughput calculations and as such suitable for GPU clusters. However, the free-energy pair interaction kernel only runs on the CPU and is an order of magnitude slower than the normal pair kernel. Furthermore, two expensive PME mesh calculations might be needed, which can currently not be offloaded to the GPU. We are working on performance improvements in the pair kernel and plan to move the PME mesh calculations to the GPU also with free-energy calculations. On GPU clusters this can double the performance of typical free-energy calculations.

3.10 Simplified free-energy calculations

Although solvation and binding free-energy calculations in GROMACS have been simplified a lot by the decoupling option which avoids editing topologies, setting up the (unphysical) path between the end states is currently still tedious, has too many technical parameters and requires manual optimization. We will remove esoteric, little used options and investigate a new, simpler soft-core scheme with more intuitive and less sensitive parameters. Also more automation will be added, such that the user does not have to edit numbers in parameters files and manually manage simulations. The user should only have to select a few method options and a scripted procedure takes care of setting up and running all simulations and the postprocessing to obtain the free-energy. Tighter integration with PMX is planned for the automation.

3.11 Implement long-term stable C++ and Python library APIs

To enable improved access to individual parts of GROMACS functionality, more of the internal parts will be exposed through a stable interface both on the C++ and Python level. The current versions of those features allow users to specify different workflows and dependencies on the Python level, as well as the use of all of the GROMACS tools from Python. Future work will be aimed at stabilizing the exposed API on the C++ level by improving modularization of the code.

3.12 Streamlining of simulation preparation tools

In addition to the core simulation engine and sampling algorithm libraries, GROMACS also packages numerous tools suitable for preparing simulation topologies and conformations. Currently the interfaces to these are complex and some tools are slow. For many, and especially novice users, it would be useful to be able to generate a run setup while only specifying a PDB file, a forcefield and a simulation length. This also simplifies setting up pipelines for studies on many different systems. For standard run setups no further user interaction should be needed, and the system can be automatically solvated in water and neutralized with counter ions. Those changes will remove the need of the users to directly

interact with the legacy *pdb2gmx* conversion tool, that has been indicated as one of the major hurdles for users starting new simulations with GROMACS.

3.13 Expansion and modernization of trajectory-analysis tool suite

While work during BioExcel has led to major improvements to the trajectory analysis tool suite and now allows replacing part of the legacy tools for writing modified trajectories and extracting information from them, there is still major work to be done on ensuring that the majority of tools are supported. Another focus point of future work is the ability to express the requirements of analysis tools regarding the format of the provided trajectory data in a programmatic way. This will ensure that users will no longer have to perform manual conversions between the results of a simulation and the input for the analysis. The project aims to fully implement those requirements for the existing tools and extending them to all other tools that are being ported to the new analysis suite.

3.14 Constant-pH simulations

Choosing the protonation state for (de)protonatable groups on proteins is problematic, because hydrogen atoms are usually not resolved in X-ray crystallography and the local acid dissociation constant (K_a) values of the ionizable groups, in most cases, are not known. Furthermore, most biomolecular systems show important changes in response to pH, and the local pH for a molecule can change when it moves through the system. Changes in protonation states can have rather large effects due to a local change in electrostatic potential. However, the chemical modification is rather small and can be mimicked by gradually moving the interactions of a proton from one site in the system to another. We have recently developed a very efficient algorithm for simulating dynamics protonation, although it needs to be refactored and fully integrated before releasing it. Dynamic protonation will enable simulating many interesting biological processes and also makes the initial choice of protonation states less critical or superfluous.

3.15 Molecular dynamics for large systems

Simulations of large systems pose particular challenges for simulation software. Large systems occur often in flow applications, but are also getting more common in the biomolecular field with simulation of virus capsids and small cells. Large systems cover larger coordinates in space, which means less absolute precision is available. The main effect that deteriorates the quality of the results is larger noise, due to rounding errors in the integration. One remedy is compiling GROMACS in double precision (for small systems single precision has proved sufficient), but that affects performance significantly and excludes the use of general purpose GPUs. A more elegant solution is storing the coordinates in fixed precision using 32-bit integers. This results in a factor 100 lower rounding errors at little extra cost. Due to the fixed precision, the rounding errors are independent of the value of the coordinates.

3.16 Flexible input format

Historically, GROMACS defined its own plain text key-value input file, implementing its own parser and requiring users to understand how to use it. This was a good decision when it was made, but now that standard formats and libraries for handling structured text input files exist, we plan to transition using these. This will eliminate many kinds of possible bugs in the code and support the modularization efforts elsewhere. Users will be able to edit the structured files in a syntax-aware editor of their choice. Developers extending the functionality of GROMACS will be able to make changes only in their new module, and not in multiple parts of the code.

3.17 Driving simulations from external inputs

Through the development of current experimental methods, more and more different methods are available to investigate protein structures and dynamics. Development started during BioExcel and recently finished now allows using experimental Cryo-EM density maps to bias MD simulations with GROMACS.

3.18 Support for Markov state model ensemble parallelism

Ensemble algorithms provide another level of parallelism, which is becoming critical to enable efficient usage of large HPC resources even for small systems such as proteins. While this is already supported in many ways in the main code base, the data analysis can often only be done using external tools, as in the case of constructing Markov state models (MSMs). Here, users would benefit from being able to use the GROMACS tools directly to perform some of the tasks needed to construct those MSMs, such as efficient clustering and feature extraction, as well as automatically setting up simulations through the Python API. It is planned to invest development effort into streamlining those processes and integrating them into a new GROMACS tool that will take advantage of the improvements to the API and the analysis tool suite.

3.19 Support for HADDOCK functionality

HADDOCK currently uses CNS as a backend for a large part of its functionality. It would be advantageous to replace parts of the HADDOCK workflow by an open source backend and GROMACS is the obvious candidate. HADDOCK needs many specific functionalities, in particular for restraints, which are not present in most molecular dynamics packages, next to very flexible selection syntax. To work towards use of GROMACS for HADDOCK we will implement dynamics atom group selections, more restraint functionality and rigid body dynamics.

4 Long term development plans for HADDOCK

During the previous iteration of the BioExcel project, we identified the demands and laid out the plans for the development of HADDOCK3, which is a complete rework of the current version. This major update aims to be both standalone and modularized, with the capability of creating custom workflows and easily integrating new modules (e.g. third party software, features, integration with GROMACS, etc).

The current version, HADDOCK 2.4, will still be developed as it will become the production version and officially distributed version as of late 2019. Its features will be gradually added to the concurrently developing HADDOCK 3.0. Such features will include: shape-based and protein-nucleotide coarse grained docking as well as refinement protocols for large assemblies, e.g. to refine low to medium resolution cryo-EM models. HADDOCK 2.4 still depends on Python 2.7, but as upstream support for Python 2 ends in 2019, we will migrate HADDOCK 2.4 to Python 3, as HADDOCK 2.4 will stay as the official version behind the web portal for the remainder of BioExcel2.

4.1 HADDOCK2.4 web server

Users mostly interact with the HADDOCK software through the webserver, so aiming towards usability and robustness, we have finished a complete rewrite of the HADDOCK webserver. All current features were ported to the new server alongside changes to account for new features that are present in the new HADDOCK2.4, such as: Cryo-EM and shape restraints, coarse grain models, automatic assignment of passive residues based on surface accessibility and multibody support for up to 20 molecules.

Our previous web server offered 7 different interfaces to run a docking simulation with different levels of control. On our new version there are only 2: In the first interface users upload their data and setup the protocol in a form, with varying degrees of complexity based on the user level, easy, expert and guru. In the second interface users launch a docking run by uploading saved, edited or programmatically generated project files in JSON format. On the higher level, power users are able to access all HADDOCK parameters (500+) giving them total control over the simulation, whereas for the easy, casual user, a much less complex interface is provided. Users can easily request different levels of access via the landing page.

HADDOCK 2.4

@Bonvinlab

WELCOME TO THE UTRECHT BIOMOLECULAR INTERACTION WEB PORTAL >>

Welcome! **HADDOCK** (High **A**mbiguity **D**riven protein-protein **D**OCKing) is an information-driven flexible docking approach for the modeling of biomolecular complexes.

HADDOCK distinguishes itself from *ab-initio* docking methods in the fact that it encodes information from identified or predicted protein interfaces in ambiguous interaction restraints (AIRs) to drive the docking process. It also allows to define specific unambiguous distance restraints (e.g. from MS cross-links) and supports a variety of other experimental data including NMR residual dipolar couplings, pseudo contact shifts and cryo-EM maps. HADDOCK can deal with a large class of modeling problems including protein-protein, protein-nucleic acids and protein-ligand complexes, including multi-bodies (N>2) assemblies.

HADDOCK is one of the **flagship software** in the EU H2020 BioExcel Center of Excellence for Biomolecular Research.

New to HADDOCK? To use the HADDOCK docking server you must have registered for an account.

[Register](#)

Our server is **easier than ever** to use. Try our new submission interface!

[Submit a new job](#)

HADDOCK is used for **excellent science** and so far it has been cited more than 5000 times!

[See our tutorials](#)

Looking for support or **questions about HADDOCK's usage?** Check our BioExcel forum!

[Get Help](#)

Server information

- The access of HADDOCK web server is **free for non-profit users** upon registration.
- Check our usage statistics and world map of users.
- The default HADDOCK **settings used by the server** can be found [here](#).
- A list of **modified amino acids supported by HADDOCK** can be found [here](#).

Figure 1 New HADDOCK2.4 web server landing page.

Figure 2 Example of the difference between EASY interface (right) and GURU interface (left) for the Input of molecules, showing different degrees of complexity.

From a technical point of view, the HADDOCK2.4 webserver is containerized using Docker containers and can be easily deployed in a time span of minutes to different locations and environments, including the cloud. In that sense, the previous iteration of the HADDOCK2.4 server located at the development and pre-production server of nestor.science.uu.nl/haddock2.4, has been recently deployed to a new cluster, accessible online at bianca.science.uu.nl/haddock2.4. The bianca server now also hosts our registration server. Once HADDOCK2.4 will be officially put into production, links to it will be added to all other pages (i.e. haddock.science.uu.nl and milou.science.uu.nl). We could also redirect those domain names to the new server, but this need to be carefully done since we have to ensure that direct links to specific services (as used by external servers connecting to HADDOCK) are not broken.

4.1.1 Expanding the server with pre-defined docking scenarios

The changes in the 2.4 server architecture and interface described above means that is it less straight-forward to use predefined protocols like the refinement interface offered in the 2.2 web server.

In order to facilitate the use of scenarios specific to a given task or system (e.g. protein-small molecule specific docking setting), we will expand the *file submit* interface with predefined recipes. We will also develop simple tools that allow users to edit and customize docking protocols based on the recipes the new server provides.

4.1.2 Result visualization

Taking advantage of the new web interface based on the Python Flask framework, we greatly improved result visualization in the 2.4 version of the HADDOCK server, moving away from the previous static manner towards use of interactive tools.

Thanks to *bokeh* Python library (bokeh.pydata.org), results are now presented in a more interactive and richer way. We have also included, for the first time in HADDOCK web server, the use of the NGL (nglviewer.org) library for visualizing and interacting with molecular structures in the browser. The different molecular structures predicted by HADDOCK2.4 web server can be inspected without downloading them and opening using any external software. Of course, the webserver still offers the possibility of downloading all the results, including a static and offline version of the results web page for user convenience.

Figure 3 HADDOCK result page showing clusters statistics (left) and their visualisation (right).

While this interactive visualization is working well for rather small assemblies (limited number of molecules), the backend scripts currently have problems with the analysis of large assemblies. We will therefore refactor those analysis script to make them more robust for complex, large and heterogeneous assemblies.

4.1.3 Results export

As a result of our work in BioExcel, the new 2.4 version of the HADDOCK server already allows the export of mmCIF, integrative modelling formatted files that combines coordinates with basic information about restraint. These are however only provided on a single model basis. In order to facilitate deposition into the new integrative model database (<https://pdb-dev.wwpdb.org>) and hereby catalyse deposition and open sharing of data, we will expand the server capabilities to capture in a single integrative modelling mmCIF file all models, their statistics and associated data. This work will be done in close collaboration with the integrative modelling task force which we participate in. (<https://pdb-dev.wwpdb.org/contributors/>).

4.2 HADDOCK2.4

Version 2.4 will be released by the end of 2019, as a package for local installation or to be used with the aforementioned web server, which will be operating over the entire duration of BioExcel2. This version incorporates features already present in previous iterations and adds coarse-grained docking, shape-based docking, support for 20 molecules and cryo-EM restraints. We aim to provide a revamped installation script, moving away from shell specific config files and using Python instead. Prior to release, its protocol scripts will be migrated to Python3.x.

4.3 HADDOCK3

The development of new modular HADDOCK3 version is ongoing and represents a major rework of the current code. In its current stable state, HADDOCK2.4 relies heavily on its CNS (Crystallography and NMR System) engine throughout its routines and with Python providing the overlaying layer connecting everything and executing the entire workflow. All the old 2.4 code is now being broken down, documented (Figure 4) and modularized.

Figure 4 Code maps exemplifying the steps taken to generate a topology (left) and how these topologies and coordinates are used (right).

4.3.1 Modular workflows

To achieve modularization we are developing a Python-CNS wrapper that can handle the communication between HADDOCK stages (CNS) and the system. This modularization also allows for the creation of custom made workflows by the development of modules. These modules will receive a standardized input and should also produce a homogeneous output that can easily be passed to the next part of the workflow. While the old static workflow was executing sequentially, rigid body docking (it0), semi flexible refinement (it1) and final solvated refinement (itw), the new HADDOCK3 framework will give fully flexibility on the protocol, allowing to create different workflows, skip stages or introduce third-party software components, for example:

1. it0 (LightDock or ZDock or FTDock, etc) + it1 HADDOCK + itw HADDOCK
2. it0 HADDOCK + it1 HADDOCK + itw GROMACS
3. no it0 + it1 HADDOCK + itw HADDOCK
4. it0 HADDOCK + no it1 + no itw

Scenario 1) HADDOCK could be replaced by other docking software that might be better suited for a thorough exploration of the interaction space in the initial docking stage, while switching to HADDOCK for the flexible refinement,

Scenario 2) replacing the old water refinement of HADDOCK by full blown molecular dynamics using GROMACS,
Scenario 3) corresponds to a refinement protocol, applied for example for large, low to medium resolution cryo-EM structures, and
Scenario 4) allows the generation of large ensemble of models by taking advantage of HADDOCK's ambiguous restraints.

4.3.2 Exascale interactome modelling

Reaching Exascale, which will be required for large scale simulation of interactomes will require efficient workflows and submission machinery. For example the human interactome is currently estimated to consist of several 100,000's of interactions, which are modulated by all kinds of post-translational modifications. This is also true in the context of large scale *in silico* drug screening campaign for example.

A possible solution to this would be to directly send the complete workflow to the batch systems, allocating a large number of threads and run the workflow and all its associated computing within the node using a multithread setup. In the scenario of interactome modelling or large scale drug screening, this means sending tens of thousands or more of those workflows directly to the batch system (instead of millions of individual jobs as it is the case of the current setup), which will clearly generate much less load to the batch system itself.

Another important aspect is efficient file I/O since HADDOCK can generate very large amounts of relatively small files. Running thousands of dockings in parallel will clearly stress the file system. By changing the way the computations are performed, sending the entire workflow to a node and limiting the I/O to that node, we expect to reach a higher efficiency both in terms of CPU usage and I/O load. This scenario is being taken into account into the development of HADDOCK2.4 and also for the upcoming 3.0 modular version.

In order to do this, we are redesigning the internal job handling machinery. While the compute intensive parts of the HADDOCK workflow are embarrassingly parallel, the pre- and post-processing steps are more sequential in nature, with, in particular, some of the post-processing being quite I/O demanding. The I/O bottleneck has been investigated in D1.2, for which we created a benchmark of 1M files and evaluated the time necessary to extract information from this huge volume of files, mimicking an exa-scale scenario.

4.4 Virtualization

HADDOCK has been containerized via Docker and Singularity technologies, recipes available in an internal repository (the containers do contain third party software which can not be freely redistributed, e.g. CNS) (<https://github.com/haddocking/virtualization>). A Docker container was built on top of the last PyCOMPSs available container as a technological test linked with WP2. We expect such containers will be key to scaling up computations on HPC

resources toward exascale interactome modelling. We will investigate the most efficient way of running those on HPC resources. This virtualisation will also facilitate HADDOCK's usage on local resources by end users.

5 Long term development plans for QM/MM with CP2K and GROMACS

5.1 Creation of robust, scalable GROMACS-CP2K interface for QM/MM

Mechanistic insights into the catalytic action of enzymes is needed to understand how these proteins have evolved to mediate chemical reactivity. Also, for improving enzymes or designing new ones, detailed understanding of the underlying reaction mechanism is essential.

Because time and spatial resolutions are difficult to access experimentally, hybrid QM/MM simulation techniques are the methods of choice to investigate enzyme reactivity; in which a small part of the system is modelled with a suitable level of ab initio or density functional theory, while the remainder is modelled with molecular mechanics force field.

However, despite the simplicity of the QM/MM concept, their application is restricted to a small group of specialized users who are often using in-house codes.

To unlock the power of QM/MM simulations to the whole biomolecular simulation community, we will develop an interface between GROMACS and CP2K that, in contrast to previous interfaces, will support QM/MM calculations under periodic boundary conditions, and provide the user with new user-friendly tools to investigate enzyme mechanisms.

This is a crucial development that will enable and accelerate the adoption of DFT-based methods available in CP2K for biomolecular modelling & simulation using hybrid QM/MM simulation. This roadmap reflects the project's transition from CPMD to CP2K, which has more wide-spread availability and uptake in the community.

5.1.1 Prototyping using existing implementation of QM/MM interface in GROMACS

The first prototype of the GROMACS/CP2K interface for performing fully-periodic QM/MM simulations will be implemented within the old QM/MM interface of GROMACS. Although that interface will be deprecated in future GROMACS releases, it serves as the basis for data exchange and interconnection between CP2K and GROMACS. Through static linking against *libcp2k* we will use the prototype interface for CP2K code optimization and testing (see section 5.2) in parallel with the development and re-factoring of a totally new interface

framework that will be based on the future MdModules framework of GROMACS, see subsection 5.1.2.

5.1.2 Modularization of the interface within GROMACS MdModules framework

Modularization of the QM/MM routines is important to maintain flexibility for linking GROMACS with quantum chemistry programs other than CP2K, our main target in BioExcel2. Maximum Flexibility will be achieved by developing an extension module within the MdModules framework, which enables plugging functionality into the GROMACS core MD engine through a single interface.

The relevant CP2K routines including any optimizations introduced as part of the work described in section 5.2 will remain inside the CP2K library (*libcp2k*), which is compiled separately and either linked to dynamically when building GROMACS with the new interface module included or incorporated directly into the resulting GROMACS executable through static linking.

The interface will ultimately be incorporated into the release version of GROMACS and thereby become available to all GROMACS users.

5.1.3 Extending parallelization of the CP2K interface for efficient usage of existing GROMACS capabilities.

In order to pave the way for ambitious GROMACS/CP2K-based QM/MM simulations on Exascale HPC resources, development of the interface will consider in detail the design choices regarding parallel execution and in particular how the existing domain decomposition within GROMACS can be made to optimally make use of MPI-parallel execution of CP2K routines, as the latter is crucial for speeding up the computationally costly QM/MM energy plus gradient calculations.

MPI sub-communicators, which can be passed to relevant CP2K routines as an alternative to using all MPI ranks (*MPI_COMM_WORLD*), will be employed for flexible parallelism, where beneficial. The efficient passing of atomic coordinates and return of QM/MM forces between GROMACS and CP2K within the existing GROMACS domain decomposition will also be taken into account.

The interface will be designed and developed iteratively, with decisions affecting performance and scalability guided by analysis of their impact for a variety of biomolecular systems in addition to the project's QM/MM use cases and on multiple hardware platforms including CPU-only and CPU+GPU nodes.

The interface test cases will exercise the interface in a variety of scenarios spanning a wide range of community uses to highlight potential problems and performance bottlenecks, e.g. in dealing with multiple QM regions, inter-timestep wavefunction handling etc., resulting in a more performance, scalable and robust implementation.

5.2 Optimization of CP2K for QM/MM through GROMACS-CP2K interface

5.2.1 Optimization of GEEP subroutines

The CP2K subroutines that compute electrostatic QM/MM interactions and that are called by GROMACS through the interface will be optimized for performance, including by the addition to the existing MPI-parallel framework of OpenMP-thread-based parallelism and tuning thereof.

In particular this applies to the subroutines *qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG* and *qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG*, which compute the long-range parts of the QM/MM forces and energies respectively with periodic boundary conditions, but extends to other (non-periodic) coupling subroutines.

These routines were identified, e.g. in deliverable D1.2 as documented at <https://github.com/bioexcel/bioexcel-exascale-co-design-benchmarks>, as together constituting a significant part of the compute time spent obtaining QM/MM forces starting from a nearly-converged wave function, i.e. ignoring DFT solution by the Quickstep module.

As the GROMACS+CP2K QM/MM solution is expected in many cases to run on GPU-equipped nodes, on which Gromacs has excellent performance, we will port the core Gaussian Expansion of the Electrostatic Potential (GEEP) subroutines to execute on GPU, using CP2K's DBCSR framework where possible.

5.2.2 Improvement of Quickstep DFT load balancing for biomolecular QM/MM

Planned inter-timestep reuse of the wavefunction as an initial guess to minimize time spent on SCF convergence for each successive step justifies the focus on optimizing core GEEP subroutines (section 5.2.1).

However depending on the size of the timestep and the degree of configurational change, DFT solution of the wave function performed by the Quickstep part of CP2K can contribute very significantly to the overall cost of computing QM/MM interactions. Indeed, in cases where the wave function from the previous timestep cannot be reused at all, its re-computation entirely dominates the runtime compared to the cost of the core GEEP subroutines.

Individual subroutines used in Quickstep have already received significant development and optimisation effort and continue to do so as they are core to CP2K's usage by its traditional user base.

However we have identified in biomolecular QM/MM simulations run entirely in CP2K that a significant load imbalance exist between subroutines *calculate_rho_elec* and *integrate_v_rspace*, which are responsible for the collocation and integration of Gaussian products respectively. These load

imbalances are not observed for traditional CP2K benchmarks such as H2O-512, H2O-DFT-LS, and LiH-HFX.

The Quickstep load balancing module, which is enabled by default, computes estimates for computational load of Quickstep tasks based on heuristics and a fit of performance data on certain cases.

We will improve the cost model by a combination of updating heuristics with performance data for biomolecular QM/MM test cases, expanding it to take into account the fraction of space that is mapped locally for a given cube and real-space grid task, and/or on-the-fly load measurement. We expect this to improve the observed load imbalance in stated subroutines and possibly also in affected MPI communication calls such as *mp_alltoall* and *mp_waitany*.

5.2.3 Optimization of CP2K subroutines and DBCSR GPU acceleration identified by performance analysis of the GROMACS-CP2K interface

Testing and performance analysis of the interface as it develops will be done by running the interface test cases driven from GROMACS on multiple hardware platforms including GPUs in order to reveal aspects impacting performance not currently identifiable by running QM/MM simulations natively within CP2K.

Performance bottlenecks thus identified within CP2K will be optimized where possible and/or used to inform and drive the design of the interface. Our GPU performance analysis will use the latest development version of the DBCSR (*Distributed Block Compressed Sparse Row*) library, which constitutes CP2K's framework for GPU acceleration of linear algebra operations.

DBCSR has recently switched to a novel procedure for generating optimized small-matrix multiplication kernel parameters that augments explicit evaluation of kernel performance for a subset of parameter space with machine learning to predict near-optimal parameter combinations. We will evaluate the performance of this new procedure and hence CP2K for biomolecular test cases and ensure it does not perform worse than for traditional CP2K / DBCSR usage.

5.3 Implementation of efficient optimizers and transition path methods in GROMACS

Although enzymes accelerate chemical reactions by orders of magnitude, their turn-over rate is usually far too slow to occur spontaneously in QM/MM simulations. Therefore, biasing approaches are needed to investigate enzyme catalysis. The development will focus on providing users with tools that can automatically locate transition states on exascale hardware.

5.3.1 Update L-BFGS optimizer in GROMACS

The development of the new optimizers will focus on finding stationary points on the potential energy surfaces of large biological systems. For that purpose, the

existing optimizers in GROMACS will be upgraded. In particular, the existing L-BFGS (limited Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno) optimizer will be updated to work efficiently within modern versions of GROMACS, using C++14 as a standard. The new L-BFGS will support Domain Decomposition within the massively parallel MPI implementations of GROMACS.

5.3.2 Micro-iterations for multiscale systems optimization.

To increase the computational efficiency of QM/MM optimizations, the number of computationally demanding quantum chemistry calculations should be minimized. The latter can be achieved within so-called micro-iterations schemes that alternate between the optimization of a few degrees of freedom at the higher level of theory (QM) and the optimization of a much larger number of degrees of freedom at the lower level of theory (MM).

To provide users with more powerful optimizers for QM/MM, a micro-iteration scheme will be implemented based on the improved L-BFGS optimizer (see subsection 5.1.1). This optimizer will be used for both the global macro-cycles at the MM level and for the micro-iterations of the QM subsystem.

5.3.3 Implementation of Nudged Elastic Band method (NEB) for optimizations of transition states in GROMACS.

For small isolated systems, transition states separating the reactants from the products can be optimized efficiently if the Hessian is available. In contrast, for large systems with periodic boundary conditions, the Hessian is not readily available. Therefore, transition state search algorithms for large systems need to rely on non-Hessian methods.

Because Chain-of-states methods do not require the Hessian, and are easy to parallelize, they are ideally suited for finding transition states in enzymes on exascale hardware.

A popular chain-of-states approach, the *Nudge Elastic Band* (NEB) method, will be implemented in GROMACS. In this approach, multiple geometries connecting the reactant and product minima are generated through interpolation and optimized individually with harmonic restraints between successive geometries.

The new NEB implementation will be based on existing functionality in GROMACS for performing simulations of multiple coupled systems (i.e. *mdrun -multi*), which provides the infrastructure to perform the optimization of each member of the transition path ensemble on a separate group of processors and communicate the information for applying the harmonic restraint between the members.

The optimization of the individual members will be performed within the micro-iteration framework (subsection 5.3.2), using the upgraded L-BFGS optimizer (subsection 5.3.1).

6 Long term development plans for PMX

While GROMACS provides a robust molecular dynamics engine providing a reliable and efficient back-end for carrying out alchemical free energy calculations, the specialized pre-processing required for such calculations can be provided by means of the pmx software package.

Currently, pmx allows for the setup and subsequent analysis of amino acid and nucleic acid mutations, as well as ligand modifications. The pmx tools can be called from the command line or via an online webserver, which supports amino and nucleic acid mutations.

6.1 Plans for the core code and usability

6.1.1 Python3

The current pmx version is based on Python 2 programming language, for which the support by the Python developers team will end in 2020. It is therefore one of the major goals for the pmx code development to transition all of the classes, modules and scripts to Python 3. The transition is planned to take place over the year 2020.

During this period, while gradually adapting the code to Python 3, two versions of pmx will co-exist: “*master*” branch based on Python 2 and “*development*” branch based on Python 3. This transition process has been already started and parts of the code are already available for testing in the “*development*” branch.

6.1.2 Conda

To allow for a convenient cross-platform installation and use of pmx, we are planning to make the pmx package available via the conda interface. The long term goal is to distribute pmx via the conda-forge channel.

6.1.3 Further modularization

While the pmx library is built in a modular manner comprising classes for handling molecular structures and topologies, the alchemical hybrid structure/topology setup is provided as a set of specialized scripts that utilize the pmx infrastructure. In some applications, for example large scale mutational scans or custom free energy workflows, it is preferable to avoid calling external scripts.

This can be circumvented by implementing the functionality of the currently available setup as independent classes of pmx. Further, it would allow the users to easily call separate modules of those classes, allowing creation of more specialized, user tailored workflows.

6.2 Mutation libraries

6.2.1 New libraries

pmx provides hybrid structure/topology generation for arbitrary amino and nucleic acid mutations. This is achieved by means of pre-generated atom mapping schemes between the residues. The sets of these mappings constitute mutation libraries, which are force field dependent. With the continuous development of new force fields, it is important to provide updated mutation libraries as well. One of the goals for pmx development is to further automate the mutation library generation procedure and provide a timely update of these libraries once the new versions of force fields are released.

6.2.2 Automated tests for mutation libraries

This is a goal closely related to section 6.2.1. Currently, every newly generated mutation library is tested in a generated topology for consistency with a set of scripts that are not part of the main pmx library. The goal is to incorporate the testing routines into pmx and enable an easy-to-use automated execution of these tests for every newly created mutation library.

6.2.3 Unified amino acid and DNA mutation libraries

Currently, the mutation libraries are separated based on the biomolecule type: amino acids and nucleic acids have different libraries, hence different force fields. In principle, this separation is not necessary, as a protein force field with the incorporated amino acid mutations can be combined with the DNA force field with the nucleic acid mutations. Such merging of the mutation libraries, although it seems to be natural, requires some internal reorganization of pmx. The unified amino acid and DNA mutation libraries will be pursued after fully transitioning pmx to Python3.

6.3 Features

6.3.1 Amino acid protonation

Estimating free energy changes upon amino acid protonation/deprotonation (pKa differences) is a frequently requested feature. From the perspective of alchemical calculations, protonation can be viewed as a particular mutation of appearing/disappearing hydrogen bound to an amino acid. In fact, the pmx mutation libraries already allow probing protonation changes for some amino acids. This feature, however, has only been probed against experimental data for several instances. Furthermore, the calculation of the proton annihilation is necessarily associated with the undesired change in the overall system charge.

While there are methods to conserve charge of the simulation box throughout such a simulation, it is important to develop an automated setup for this procedure. All in all, for pmx to provide robust predictions of the pKa shifts, it is necessary to implement this specific simulation setup and validate it against experimental data.

6.3.2 Post-translational modifications

Amino acid mutations representing post-translational modifications is another frequently requested pmx feature. To implement this feature, it is necessary to develop a flexible generation of arbitrary mutations in a library.

This functionality is in part comparable to ligand modifications, where alchemical morphs between arbitrary compounds are created. In addition, the incorporation of post-translational modifications requires extending the core pmx responsible for identifying and handling entries in the mutation libraries. These changes comprise a long term goal for pmx development.

6.3.3 Covalent modifications

Alchemical bond breaking is advised against in the standard free energy calculation setups. There are situations, however, where it is not possible to avoid annihilating a bond, e.g. proline involving mutations.

In these cases, carefully designed topology generations may prove it feasible to allow the disappearance of a bond, e.g. the pmx “*development*” branch already readily allows proline mutations that involve ring opening/closure and thus covalent bond breaking/formation. The adaptation of such schemes in more general scenarios requires further exploration. A long term goal is for pmx to support at least for some common alchemical covalent modifications.

6.3.4 Workflows

pmx is already capable of generating input for various alchemical modifications, i.e. all the necessary preparation and pre-processing. The next step of the actual free energy calculation itself is currently left fully for the user to carry out. One of the main goals for pmx development is to provide a set of workflows that would allow a convenient simulation setup using the readily available hybrid structure/topology input. The workflows will cover both the equilibrium and non-equilibrium free energy calculation protocols using pmx as the input generator and GROMACS as the simulation engine.

7 Roadmaps

Figure 5 Development roadmap for GROMACS

Bioexcel 2

Figure 6 Development roadmap for HADDOCK

Figure 7 Development roadmap for PMX

Figure 8 Development roadmap for CP2K

Appendix: Status of pilot codes

GROMACS code development status

☑ - Complete

☑ - Work in progress

	End of BioExcel1	PM18 BioExcel2	PM36 BioExcel2
Official distribution version	v2019	v2020.4	
Development version(s)	release-2020	release-2021	
Supported features			
• Python API	☑ (v0.1)	☑ (v0.2)	
• Modular simulator	☑	☑	
• Density fitting	no	☑	
• Accelerated weight histogram sampling method	☑	☑	
• AWH free-energy perturbation	no	☑	planned
• Multiple time stepping on CPU	no	☑	planned
• Multiple time stepping on GPU	no	no	planned
• GPU only simulations	no	☑	
• Update groups	☑	☑	
• OpenCL PME offloading	☑	☑	
• Intel iGPU OpenCL	☑	☑	
• ARM SVE Support	no	☑	planned
• SYCL Support	no	☑	planned
• Non-bonded benchmark tool	no	☑	
• Stochastic cell rescaling	no	☑	planned

• Containerization (Docker/Singularity)	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
• QM/MM interface to CP2K	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
• Topology pre-processing for QM/MM	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
• Nudged-Elastic-Band reaction pathway optimizer	no		planned
Code Health			
• Version control (Gerrit/GitLab)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
• Unit tests	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
• Integration tests	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
• Semantic versioning	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
• Code quality - clang format, clang-tidy, doxygen	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
• Quarterly KPI checking (removal of legacy code, cyclomatic complexity)	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
• User feedback integration label	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
• Submodule integration (tests/examples)	no	<input type="checkbox"/>	planned
• Physical validation suite	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
• Integration of QM/MM into build and testing environment	no	<input type="checkbox"/>	

GROMACS modular code development status

	End of BioExcel1	PM18 BioExcel2	PM36 BioExcel2
Live status	v2019	v2020	
Development version	release-2020	release-2021	

Modules			
• MDMModules	✓	✓	
• fine-grained modularisation	no	no	✓
• Trajectory analysis	✓	✓	
• mdrun	-	✓	
• Defined API boundary	no	✓	planned

HADDOCK code development status

✓ - Complete

✓ - Work in progress

	End of BioExcel1	PM18 BioExcel2	Planned PM36 BioExcel2
Official distribution version	v2.2	v2.4 (4 releases, latest is September)	v2.5
Development version(s)	v2.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • v2.5 (port to python3) • v3.0 (complete modular rewrite) 	v3.0
Supported features in v2.4			
- Cryo-EM restraints	✓	✓	✓
- Support for up to 20 molecules	✓	✓	✓
- Distance-dependent dielectric	✓	✓	✓
- C6 symmetry restraints	✓	✓	✓

- Coarse graining for proteins	✓	✓	✓
- Coarse graining for nucleic acids	✓	✓	✓
- Support for cyclic peptides	no	✓	✓
- Automatic detection of D-amino acids	no	✓	✓
- Option for automatically definition of HIS protonation states based on electrostatic energy	no	✓	✓
- Switched to official 1/2 letter code for RNA/DNA	no	✓	✓
- Option to fix molecules in their original position	no	✓	✓
- Support for glycosylated proteins	no	✓	✓
- Support for glycan docking	no	✓	✓
- Support for shape restraints	no	✓	✓
- Shape-based SAXS docking protocol	no	✓	✓
- Centroid-based refinement protocol	no	✓	✓
- Support for explicit membrane	no	no	Planned
- Containerization (Singularity)	no	✓	✓
- Containerization (Docker)	no	no	Planned
Increased efficiency in v2.4/v2.5			
- Various analysis options for increased efficiency	✓	✓	✓
- Removal of bottlenecks in workflow machinery to all more concurrent docking	no	✓	✓

runs (a covid19 response)			
- Packing in Singularity and integration with PyCOMMPs	no	✓	✓
- Improved error detection and handling for more robust execution	no	✓	✓
Code Health			
- Version control (GitHub)	✓	✓	✓
- Integration tests	✓ (27 scenarios)	✓ (40 scenarios)	✓
- Semantic versioning	no	✓	✓
- Online software manual v2.4/2.5	no	✓	✓
- Code quality - Linter, logging	no	✓ - v2.5	✓
- Submodule integration (tests/examples)	no	✓	✓

HADDOCK web server development status

Note: Haddock v2.2 webserver has gone into maintenance mode after the end of Bioexcel 1.

	End of BioExcel1		HADDOCK2.4 PM18 BioExcel2	Planned PM36 BioExcel2
	v2.2	v2.4	v2.4	v2.5
Status	Production	Development	Production	Production
Web Server Features				
- Single Sign On (via EGI CheckIn)	✓	✓	✓	✓
- GDPR compliant	✓	✓	✓	✓
- Docker integration	no	✓	✓	✓

- - Continuous Integration pipeline (Jenkins)	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Interactive result pages	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Heavy validation of input parameters	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Molecule type-specific optimal settings	no	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- User workspace	no	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- - File submission (reproducible parameter file)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- New molecule type: Shape	no	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- New molecule type: Dummy	no	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- New molecule type: Glycan	no	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- New molecule type: Glycosylated Proteins	no	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Refinement interface	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	no	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Reporting API	no	no	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Filtering of solvent accessible active residues	no	no	no	Planned
- User documentation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	no	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

HADDOCK3.0 modular code development status

	End of BioExcel1	PM18 BioExcel2	Planned PM36 BioExcel2
Live status	-	Development	Pre-release
Development version	-	alpha 2	beta
Modules			
- Pre-processing	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Topology generation	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Rigid Body sampling	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Semi flexible refinement	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Solvent explicit refinement	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Scoring (EM only)	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Analysis	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Clustering (FCC)	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Coarse-Grain topology	-	-	Planned
- Scoring (EM+MD)	-	-	Planned
- Support for shapes	-	-	Planned
- Support for small ligand docking	-	-	Planned
- Support for glycosylated proteins	-	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Support for glycans	-	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Integration with another docking engine (LighDock)	-	-	Planned
- Support for GROMACS Python/API	-	-	Planned
- Python API support for bioBB	-	-	Planned

Scenarios (workflows)			
- CAPRI scoring	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Protein-Protein docking with distance restraints	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Automated Benchmarking (BM5)	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Refinement	-	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Coarse-Grained docking	-	-	Planned
- Membrane Docking (via LightDock integration)	-	-	Planned
Supported restraints			
- Distance restraints	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Code Health			
- Version control (GitHub)	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Unit tests	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Semantic versioning	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Submodule integration (tests/examples)	-	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Integration tests	-	-	Planned
- Online software manual	-	-	Planned
- Code quality - Linter, logging	-	-	Planned

pmx status - Complete - Work in progress

	End of BioExcel1	PM18 BioExcel2	PM36 BioExcel2
pmx webserver: main framework	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

pmx webserver: amino acid mutations	✓	✓	
pmx webserver: DNA mutations	✓	✓	
pmx webserver: tripeptide database	✓	✓	
Ligand modifications: atom mapping	✓	✓	
Ligand modifications: topology generation	✓	✓	
Ligand modifications: ligand mapping	✓	✓	
Ligand modifications: cycle closure correction	✓	✓	
Python3: core modules	✓	✓	
Python3: amino acid mutations	✓	✓	
Python3: nucleic acid mutations	✓	✓	
Python3: ligand modifications (atom mapping)		✓	
Python3: ligand modifications (topology generation)		✓	
Python3: ligand modifications (ligand mapping)			Planned
Free energy calculation workflows	✓	✓	Planned
Absolute free energy support		✓	Planned
Python3: pmx webserver amino acid mutations			Planned
Python3:			Planned

pmx webserver DNA mutations			
Proline mutation support		✓	
Arbitrary covalent mutation support			Planned

CP2K status

✓ - Complete

✓ - Work in progress

	PM18 BioExcel2	PM36 BioExcel2
Addition of functionality to enable GROMACS-CP2K interface		
Add cell size change functionality in CP2K through call to libcp2k to enable pressure coupling with GROMACS	✓	
Optimisation of GEEP QM/MM force & energy subroutines		
Addition of OpenMP-threaded parallelism	✓	
Enabling offload to GPU	✓	
Optimisation of subroutines identified by performance analysis of the GROMACS-CP2K interface		
Optimisation of new DBCSR small matrix multiplication acceleration scheme for biomolecular problems		Planned
Optimisation of further CP2K and/or DBCSR subroutines for CPU & GPU platforms based on analysis of interface performance on range of community test cases	✓	
Improvement of Quickstep DFT load balancing for biomolecular QM/MM		
Updating Quickstep task-based load balancing heuristics		Planned
Implementing on-the-fly load measurement		stretch target